

POLICING IN MINING: EFFECT OF STRESS ON POLICE ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to identify the effect of stressors on organizational commitment and how organizational commitment affects the performance of police personnel on duty in mining areas. Stressors explored in this study consist of Factors Intrinsic to Job, Organizational Context, Role in Organization, Relationship at Work, Career Development, and Extra Organizational Factors. The quantitative result indicated that organizational context negatively influences organizational commitment. The results also confirm recent research regarding the positive effect of commitment on police performance. In general, stressors tested in this study found to be less harm to the commitment of police officers working in complex and conflictprone economic sectors such as the mining sector. However, it is worth noting that although some stressors do not have a significant effect, the negative influence of stressors such as factors Intrinsic to the job and extra organizational factors is known to exist and can have a negative impact on commitment.

Keywords: Commitment, Mining sector, Police, Stressor

INTRODUCTION

As a country with abundant natural resources, Indonesia has the potential for mining materials that can support the country's economy. This potential provides a large enough contribution to state revenue. Recognizing these potential, the Indonesian government strives to maintain the conduciveness of mining investment through various regulations that support the creation of a friendly and supportive mining investment climate. It includes efforts to maintain the conduciveness and security of existing mining objects as stated in Presidential Decree No. 63 of 2004 concerning the Security of National Vital Objects in conjunction with Law No. 2 of 2002 which instructing Indonesian National Police to compile guidelines of security system for vital national objects as an effort to provide protection and public services.

The regulation on securing vital national objects is intended to minimize and even prevent the impact of disturbances and threats to vital national objects that can result in humanitarian

disasters, disruption of government, threats to national security and defense, and the most avoided is the destruction of the results of national development. The policy issued by the government cannot be separated from the fact that the mining sector is one sector that tends to create various problems, especially at the local level. These problems include social, economic, legal, and environmental issues. Various studies that examine issues in the mining sector reveal that the presence of mining corporations and their activities creates various conflicts, especially conflicts at the local level where mining activities take place (Munwarah, 2015; Resosudarmo et al., 2009; Andrews et al., 2017; Nugraha, 2017). This kind of conflict often arises and creates quite severe security problems in various mining areas in Indonesia. These various conflicts trigger legal problems that create unfavorable conditions in the mining environment (Kadir and Suaib (2020).

Data from the Indonesian Forum for the Environment (2011) reveals that one of the provinces with the potential for mining conflicts in Southeast Sulawesi Province. These conflict areas are spread over several prominent mining locations in South Konawe, Konawe Islands, and North Konawe. The Southeast Sulawesi Regional Police (2020) data mapping about conflict vulnerabilities in mining areas reveals that the conflicts that often arise are those related to illegal mining activities and social conflicts involving local and foreign workers that lead to security and legal issues.

Legal problems that often occur in the mining environment require serious attention from local and national governments. Law enforcement institutions such as the police have an essential role in maintaining the company's operations in carrying out its mining activities. In Indonesia, the police at the local level where mining activities take place face their challenges in ensuring a conducive mining environment. It puts police officers in a difficult position because they have to work in an unfavorable environment that can trigger psychological disorders, especially stress (Garbarino, Cuomo, Chiorri, and Magnavita Garbarino et al., 2013; Lucas, Weidner, and Janisse Lucas et al., 2012). This psychological disorder cannot be separated from the fact that the police organization is one of the organizations that is considered prone to stress because of its operational nature, which requires the personnel in it to work extra in the law enforcement process, which can sometimes threaten personal safety (Hammad, 2012; Vuorensyrjä and Mälkiä, 2011; Magnavita and Garbarino 2013).

Over the decades, stress on police officers has been extensively studied (Brown and Campbell, 1990; Mansell and Brough, 2005; Hart et al., 1995; Euwema et al., 2004; Brown, 2000; Chan, 2007; Toch, 2000). Nevertheless, these various studies, especially recent studies, look at these stressful conditions based on settings where police officers typically work, such as on-foot traffic control (Hammad et al. 2012; Marois et al., 2019), in border areas (Nisar and Rasheed, 2019), front-line officer (Jonyo, 2015; Duran and Bishop, 2019; Sadiq, 2020). Police involvement in conflict-prone sectors such as the mining sector can encourage psychological disorders such as stress. As stated by Marois et al. (2019), the work environment complexity can influence the stress level of police officers. It may include dangerous factors that arise in the work environment in which the police are on duty (He, Zhao, & Archbold, 2002; Donald et al., 2005; Vischer, 2007;) or demands for a heavy and

irregular workload (Violanti and Aron, 1994; Sadiq, 2020), that must be followed by the police when carrying out monitoring and security in the mining environment.

Furthermore, the effect of stress on police officers commitment has been widely studied (Lambert et al., 2021; Ates and Ihtiyaroglu, 2019; Hunter and Thatcher, 2007; Jeramillo, 2005; Kuo, 2015), as well as the effect of stress on their performance (Marois et al. al, 2019; Vischer, 2007; Nisar, 2019; Jonyo, 2015; Duran et al., 2018; Hammad, 2012; Brunetto, 2017). However, research related to the effect of stress on the commitment and performance of police officers involved in complex and conflict-prone economic sectors such as the mining sector has not been widely studied. Therefore, it is crucial to know the extent to which stress affects the commitment and performance of police officers in different work environment contexts, especially in the mining sector in Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational Commitment

The existence of an organization is strongly influenced by the organizational commitment variable (Ates and Ihtiyaroglu, 2019). High organizational commitment possessed by employees can enable them to continue to survive and support organizational achievement (Caught and Shadur, 2000; Meyer & Allen, 1997). The organizational commitment represents the bond that individuals have to their organization, which is driven by moral support and the perceived similarity to the organization's values. Robbins and Judge (2013: 100) view organizational commitment as an individual's alignment with organizational goals, shown through the desire to maintain the organization membership. Organizational commitment is a condition where individuals have a high sense of belonging to the organization and are willing to sacrifice to achieve the expected goals.

Various factors influence organizational commitment. Ly et al. (2021) found that leadership, meeting effectiveness, and job satisfaction affect organizational commitment. Nguyen & Ngo (2020) found that psychological capital, which comprises four different components: self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience, has a positive relationship with commitment. Kawiana et al. (2021) found that psychological climate influences organizational commitment, which also confirms previous research, such as research conducted by Parker et al. (2003) and James et al. (1990).

Job Stressor

In general, stress refers to experiences associated with nervousness, tension, and tension (Cooke & Rousseau, 1984). Jex and Beehr (1992) define stress as work tension, a reaction or result of experience with stressors, covering three areas: psychological/emotional, physical, and behavioral. Selye (1980: 6) describes stress as an organism's specific reaction to a stimulant that causes change. Stress can also be described as tension or pressure felt at work (Motowidlo et al., 1986; Van Dyne et al., 2002). The tension felt by this individual can be in the form of psychological or physiological tension (Ünsal, 2012), which can be related to a

sense of time pressure, anxiety, and worries related to work tasks (Hunter and Thatcher, 2007).

Hunter and Thatcher (2007) state that stressors are antecedents or stimuli of job tension. It can arise at the individual level, such as role conflict and role ambiguity, and at the organizational level, such as budget cuts and layoffs mergers and acquisitions. The literature review conducted by Jaramillo et al. (2005) found that the relationship between the causes of stress and stress and its impact on commitment should be viewed in terms of the work context. As pointed out by Narayanan et al. (1999) that what constitutes a stressor may differ across jobs. It is because different types of work have different environmental variations to provide different effects or stimulation to stress.

In the context of law enforcement, the work carried out by police officers has several similarities with other types of work when viewed from the point of view of job interactions (Kiely and Peek, 2002). However, there are significant differences in job characteristics because police organizations have a more dangerous and stressful work environment than most other work environments. In addition, as a public organization, the police have different goals from private organizations because this organization is not profit-oriented but is oriented towards law enforcement, such as reducing crime and increasing public welfare (Jaramillo et al., 2005).

The peculiarities of police officers' work characteristics as described above also affect the causes of stress on the police officers. Kiely and Peek (2002) explained that organizational culture in law enforcement is different from most private sector organizations. The law enforcement culture is a culture formed in a semi-military manner that is very bound by strict rules and is a monopoly in service.

In addition, the police also have to deal with and serve a heterogeneous and complex society. These significant differences in organizational culture produce different stress-causing factors.

In the context of police institutions, various studies identify the antecedents of the organizational commitment of police personnel (Sun et al., 2021). Some of these factors are related to organizational and job characteristics (Baek, 2020; Frank et al., 2020; Johnson, 2015; Shim et al., 2015) and factors related to emotional states such as levels of tension, psychological well-being, stress from work-family related conflicts, and job satisfaction (Nalla et al., 2020; Qureshi et al., 2019).

Factor Intrinsic to Job

Work intrinsic factors that cause stress are related to factors that negatively affect mental and physical health that arise from environmental conditions in which individuals work (Cooper & Marshall, 1976). Kuo (2015) states that these factors can include a poor physical environment, hazardous workplace conditions, physical hazards, uncomfortable working hours, and excessive workloads. Many of the above factors are experienced by the police because they tend to be vulnerable to various risks when carrying out their work. Intrinsic

factors that are not good can increase stress on police officers, which can result in psychological considerations about their existence in the organization. McCarty and Skogan's (2013) research shows that police personnel on duty in the field with high exposure to danger are prone to burnout. According to Hakanen, Schaufeli, & Ahola (2008), individuals who feel stressed because they feel they do not get sufficient support in carrying out their work will tend to have low work involvement, which can reduce organizational commitment.

H1: Factor Intrinsic to Job negatively influences organizational commitment

Organizational Context

According to Cooper and Marshall (1976), employee involvement in the organization, especially in decision-making, influences the pressure felt by employees. In the context of the work of police officers, semi-military organizations tend not to provide opportunities for them in the decision-making process so that it can have an impact on a sense of involvement in the organization, which can put pressure on its own. In addition to limited decision making, lack of organizational support and unequal or fair workloads become sources of stress in the organizational context (Pienaar & Rothmann, 2006). Some of these factors can reduce individual work involvement to reduce the sense of belonging within individuals, reducing their commitment to the organization (Hakanen, Schaufeli, & Ahola, 2008).

H2: Organizational Context negatively influences organizational commitment

Role in Organization

The roles of employees in an organization include role ambiguity and role conflict being the main elements that trigger work stress. Police officers tend to face this problem wherein carrying out their duties as law enforcement officers often have to face problems requiring them to carry out multiple roles (Mansoor et al., 2011). Police who are required to complete tasks quickly will feel an excessive workload, causing them to lose emotion, time, and energy (Sadiq, 2020). Wang et al. (2014) stated that stress on police officers arises because they are placed in a difficult position in their role so that it can cause emotional reactions as a result of job demands that are not per their abilities and resources. Dewe, O'Driscoll, & Cooper (2010) argue that when individuals experience stress due to their role in the organization, their job satisfaction will decrease, which can negatively affect organizational commitment.

H3: Role in Organization negatively influences organizational commitment

Relationship at Work

Relationships at work are related to the interpersonal relationships that police officers have with co-workers, supervisors, and subordinates when in a supervisory role (Cooper and Marshall, 1976). Van (2016) revealed that organizational culture factors such as hierarchy tend to limit interactions between individuals, which can impact the emergence of stress as has been explained that the task of law enforcement is a job that has strict rules and supervision so that it can have a psychological impact on police officers in carrying out their duties. Thompson et al. (2005) revealed that potentially, relationships at work, both with co-workers and supervisors, can reduce the adverse effects of stress. Research by Ganster,

Fusilier, and Mayes (1986) found that support from supervisors and co-workers is an essential source of reducing stress. Thus, if the relationship between individuals and co-workers and supervisors is not supportive, it can encourage stress and discomfort in the organization. Kuo (2015) argues that workplace relationships can negatively influence the organizational commitment of police personnel.

H4: Relationship at Work negatively influences organizational commitment

Career Development

Career development is related to employee's perceptions of their future (Cooper & Marshall, 1976). In a study conducted by Nisar and Rasheed (2020), satisfaction with career development dramatically affects the stress of police officers. Burke (1989), who discussed the five phases of a career in the police force, found that lower-level police officers such as mid-career police officers exhibited high job stress, low job satisfaction, and work-family, which impacted their performance. Individuals tend to have high work stress if they feel the lack of feedback that the organization can provide for what they have done. It can lead to feelings of disappointment and hatred towards the organization so that they will feel the lack of value for the benefits that have been provided by the organization, which can lead to a decrease in their organizational commitment (Cropanzano et al., 2003).

H5: Career Development negatively influences organizational commitment

Extra Organizational Factors

Extra Organizational Factors relate to external factors that can create tension and stress for individuals. Tension arises from factors outside of work, such as elements of social life that also affect the work environment. Sadiq (2020), in his research, found that social life, such as family conflicts, also affected the level of stress he felt. In mining, police assigned to mining areas have difficulty dividing their time between their duties and social life. It tends to cause stress, such as the opinion expressed by Mansour and Commeiras (2015) that individuals who cannot simultaneously carry out responsibilities related to work and family tend to stress because of their inability to share roles triggering work-family conflict, which in turn triggers emotions. These emotions affect outside the organization and can also be carried over into the organization, which can disrupt the individual's commitment to the organization.

H6: Extra Organizational Factors negatively influences organizational commitment

Police Performance

Performance plays a vital role for individuals and organizations (Saleem, Nauman, and Zahra, 2019). Jagannathan (2014) defines employee performance as the results shown by financial and non-financial consequences that directly relate to organizational performance and success. Mensah (2015) argues that performance can be measured through different mechanisms (Mensah, 2015). Regarding the performance of police personnel, Whitaker (1982), states that measuring police performance is not accessible because the police department performs many different jobs.

Furthermore, various factors have a significant influence on improving performance. One of them is organizational commitment (Allen & Meyer, 1997). According to Hunter and Thatcher (2007), commitment influences job performance through identification and internalization. In other words, when individuals can identify themselves as part of the organization and internalize it in a high sense of belonging, the individual will be able to provide the best for the organization where he works. Individuals will try to achieve and show high performance in carrying out the tasks assigned to them because they believe that what they do is very important for the achievement of organizational goals and values (NGUYEN and NGO, 2020). Recent studies have shown that commitment has a positive effect on performance (NGUYEN and NGOs, 2020; Astuty and Udin, 2020)

H7: Commitmen Factors positively influences performance.

METHOD

The research is quantitative research by applying a descriptive study. The research apply explanatory research which is emphasizes studying the situation or problem to explain the relationship between variables (Saunders et al., 2007:134). The population in this study were all field police personel totaling 120 people who served 6 Sectoral Police Offices located in mining areas in Southeast Sulawesi which were distributed into two regencies where large mining companies were located, namely in North Konawe Regency and South Konawe Regency. Meanwhile, the sampling technique used the census sampling method by taking the entire population as the research sample.

The five-point Likert scale was employed to rate the questionnaire items, ranging from 1 indicating strongly disagree and five indicating strongly agree. Stressors as independent variables consisting of Factors Intrinsic to Job, Organizational Context, Role in Organization, Relationship at Work, Career Development, and Extra Organizational Factors were measured by adapting the questionnaire developed by Kuo (2005) by adjusting statement items relevant the context of the study. The organizational commitment variable is measured based on organizational commitment proposed by Allen and Meyer (1997), consisting of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

Meanwhile, the measurement of police performance uses indicators for measuring the performance of police personnel as regulated in the Regulation of the Head of the National Police of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2 of 2018, which consists of leadership, service orientation, communication, emotional control, integrity, empathy, organizational commitment, initiative, discipline, cooperation, quality, and quantity. Performance measurement using standards set by the Indonesian National Police Institute is considered relevant for measuring the performance of police officers in this study because these performance measurement indicators have different characteristics compared to performance measurement in organizations in general. Information was collected through the distribution of questionnaires that had previously been tested for validity and reliability. Data analysis used the partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) technique by utilizing

the Smart PLS 3.0 application program. This technique is suitable for testing hypotheses about the observed and latent variables (Hair et al., 2011). There are two stages of measurement analysis using this technique: the evaluation of the measurement model or outer model and the evaluation of the structural model or inner model.

RESULTS

Testing for Convergent and Discriminant Validity

We tested Cronbach's alpha, average variance extracted (AVE), and composite reliability (CR) to ensure convergent validity for each construct. Menrut Hair et al. (2011) The appropriate threshold values for Cronbach's alpha, AVE, and CR are 0.6, 0.5, and 0.7, respectively. In addition, testing is also carried out on each indicator's outer loading, which must have a threshold value above 0.6 as suggested by Hair et al. (2011), so items that do not reach the threshold should be discarded.

The results of the outer loading (Figure 2) show that all items have a value greater than the threshold value where the loading value is in the range from 0.702 to 0.980 (Table 1). In addition, Cronbach's alpha value is above the threshold of 0.6., the average variance extracted (AVE) has a value above 0.5., and composite reliability (CR) has a value above 0.7, which indicates that all items meet the validity and reliability criteria (Table 3). 1). Furthermore, to check discriminant validity, we used the Heterotrait-Monotrite (HTMT) criteria. Henseler et al. (2015) proposed checking the validity through this method because it has a higher level of specificity and sensitivity (97% to 99%) compared to the cross-loading criteria(0.00%) and Fornell-Lacker (20.82%). To determine the threshold in this HTMT test, some authors suggest a threshold of 0.85 (Kline, 2011), but in this study, we use the threshold suggested by Gold (2001), who proposes a value of 0.90 as the test threshold value. The results of Table 2 indicate that discriminant validity criteria are met.

Figure 1: Result of Outer Loading

Table 1: Reliability and Validity Analysis

Latent Variables	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Job Performance	24	0.735-0.876	0.976	0.977	0.977	0.644
Organizational Commitment	12	0.857-0.882	0.966	0.967	0.970	0.731
Factor Intrinsic to Job	9	0.786-0.977	0.969	1.042	0.970	0.784
Organizational Context	8	0.868-0.939	0.965	0.968	0.970	0.803
Role in Organization	2	0.924-0.943	0.853	0.864	0.931	0.871
Relationship at Work	6	0.763-0.939	0.934	0.940	0.948	0.753
Career Development	6	0.842-0.922	0.942	0.943	0.954	0.776
Extra-Organizational Factor	6	0.930-0.968	0.980	1.001	0.983	0.907

Table 2: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	CD	EF	FJ	P	C	OR	RW	RO
CD								
EF	0,183							
FJ	0,154	0,143						
P	0,890	0,184	0,130					
C	0,836	0,126	0,134	0,867				
OC	0,532	0,098	0,061	0,510	0,517			
RW	0,627	0,257	0,172	0,672	0,692	0,831		
RO	0,602	0,035	0,106	0,614	0,625	0,893	0,746	

Notes: CD: Career Development; EF: Extra-Organizational Factor; FJ: Factor Intrinsic to Job; P: Job Performance; C: Organizational Commitment; OC: Organizational Context; RW: Relationship at Work; RO: Role in Organization

Structural Model Results

Structural model testing is done first by looking at the R2 value of the endogenous construct, namely organizational commitment and performance. The value of R2 shows the values of 0.719, and 0.721 for the organizational commitment construct and the performance construct, respectively. The value reflects a high fit to explain over 70% of the variance (Henseler et al., 2009). Furthermore, a nonparametric bootstrapping test was conducted (Wetzels et al., 2009) to see the structural model and test the research hypotheses. Table 3 shows the value of the structural model after the PLS analysis is carried out. The analysis results show that of the seven hypotheses proposed, there are only two accepted hypotheses, namely hypothesis 2 and hypothesis 7.

Table 3: Structural Model Result

Hypotheses	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Decision
H1	-0,001	0,019	0,985	Unsupported
H2	-0,300	2,733***	0,007	Supported
H3	0,217	2,803***	0,005	Unsupported
H4	0,420	3,656***	0,000	Unsupported
H5	0,587	6,141***	0,000	Unsupported
H6	-0,043	0,786	0,432	Unsupported
H7	0,849	14,988***	0,000	Supported

Notes: *p < 0.1; ***p < 0.01.

DISCUSSION

The main objective of this study is to identify the effect of stressors on organizational commitment and how organizational commitment affects the performance of police personnel on duty in mining areas. Stressors consist of Factors Intrinsic to Job, Organizational Context, Role in Organization, Relationship at Work, Career Development, and Extra Organizational Factors. Based on the inner model analysis results, it is known that there are only two accepted hypotheses (H2 and H7). Organizational context negatively influences organizational commitment with a critical factor value of 0.007. The organizational context explores the response of police personnel related to a conducive and pleasant work climate, a fair sifting system, a fair allocation of tasks, and the allocation of other additional tasks. The poor perception of police personnel towards the organizational context harms organizational commitment, which is in line with research by Pienaar & Rothmann (2006), Hakanen, Schaufeli, & Ahola (2008), and Cicei (2012).

Furthermore, the relationship between commitment to performance was positive and significant with a critical factor value of 0.000. The results of this study confirm recent research regarding the positive effect of commitment on performance (NGUYEN and NGOs, 2020; Astuty and Udin, 2020). In the context of law enforcement institutions such as the police in Indonesia, the high commitment shown by police personnel cannot be separated

from the organizational culture that surrounds the institution. Hunter and Thatcher (2007) argue that commitment influences individual performance through identification and internalization. Individuals will try to achieve and show high performance in carrying out the tasks assigned to them because they believe that what they do is very important for the achievement of organizational goals and values (NGUYEN and NGO, 2020).

Meanwhile, hypothesis 1, which tested the negative effect of the Intrinsic to Job Factor on organizational commitment, was insignificant ($p > 0.01$). Although the first hypothesis is not accepted, it appears that the value of the relationship between the Intrinsic to Job Factor and commitment is negative. The Intrinsic to Job Factor explores the responses of police personnel to the support they receive while performing their jobs. These include support for adequate work equipment, hardware equipment, and housing facilities. In addition, this intrinsic factor also looks at the nature of the work they do, including job allocation, labor adequacy, workload, work hazards, and working hours. Interestingly, although the intrinsic to job factor has a negative value, it does not significantly reduce the organizational commitment of police personnel assigned to strategic economic objects such as the mining sector. It is contrary to the research results by McCarty and Skogan (2013) regarding the burnout vulnerability of police personnel on duty in the field with high exposure to danger. Furthermore, the results of this study also contradict Hakanen, Schaufeli, & Ahola (2008), who found that individuals who do not get support will feel stress, which can reduce their work involvement and reduce their organizational commitment.

Furthermore, Hypothesis 3, which examines the effect of the role in the organization construct on organizational commitment, is also rejected where the results of the inner loading model show the opposite, namely the role in the Organization construct has a positive and significant effect on commitment. The role in organization construct explores the response of police officers to their role in the organization, including clarity of job descriptions and clarity of laws and regulations that must be obeyed and implemented. Because the police institution is an organization that has clear and strict regulations and culture, respondents tend to give a positive response to this construct. Clarity of roles in this organization encourages high commitment, whereas role ambiguity or role ambiguity can reduce organizational commitment (Wang et al., 2014; Dewe, O'Driscoll, & Cooper, 2010)

Hypothesis 4 examines the negative influences of the Relationship at Work construct on organizational commitment. The results of the inner loading show that hypothesis 4 is rejected, where the results of the analysis show that the Relationship at Work construct has a significant positive effect on commitment. This construct explores an individual's relationship with co-workers and their immediate supervisor or supervisor at work. These two sections cover relationships in sharing experiences and support provided by colleagues and communication and direct supervisor support in decision making. Thompson et al. (2005) revealed that relationships at work, both with colleagues and supervisors, can reduce the adverse effects of stress and vice versa. The task of law enforcement is a job with strict rules and supervision to have a psychological impact on police officers in carrying out their duties. However, this does not harm the commitment of the police. In other words, police officers

who work in mining areas do not experience difficulties interacting with colleagues and superiors. It can happen because the police organization has a clear and structured line of command so that they do not face significant obstacles in building relationships in the workplace. This rejected hypothesis contradicts the results of Kuo's research (2015).

Hypothesis 5 examines the negative influence of Career Development negatively on organizational commitment. The inner loading construct shows different results, so this hypothesis is rejected. Based on the structural model results, it is known that, on the contrary, Career Development positively influences organizational commitment. This construct explores responses related to career development in police organizations that include information, promotion policies, promotion rules, and training provided by organizations to improve the quality of work in law enforcement. According to Cropanzano et al. (2003), individuals can have high work stress if they feel a lack of feedback from the organization, which reduces organizational commitment. However, in the context of the police institution, the opposite can happen where clear career paths and procedures are undertaken by personnel who will carry out promotions are positive aspects that respondents consider. So that it raises a positive perception of this construct, mainly if it is associated with the organizational commitment they have. The binding laws and regulations in this promotion process make them calmer in carrying out their duties. The same applies to the training and self-development process where police personnel has clear training procedures and schedules. The results of this study contradict Burke (1989) and Nisar and Rasheed (2020).

Hypothesis 6 examines the negative influence of Extra Organizational Factors on organizational commitment. Inner loading shows that the effect of this construct on commitment is not significant ($p > 0.01$), so the proposed hypothesis is rejected. This construct explores the responses related to the influence of external factors, which include personal problems such as family support, financial problems, and family burdens, as well as other external issues such as the involvement of politicians, public assessments of police performance, and media portrayals of the negative image of the police. Although hypothesis 6 is not accepted, it appears that the value of the relationship between the extra-organizational factor construct and commitment is negative. This value indicates that factors from outside the organization, such as personal problems and socio-political problems, negatively influence police personnel's commitment. Although this influence is not significant, its existence still deserves attention. The results of the analysis on hypothesis 6 are in line with the results of Kuo's research (2015) and contradict the results of the research of Dewe, O'Driscoll, & Cooper (2010).

CONCLUSION

Human resources have a vital role in every organization. Recognizing this critical role, organizations should pay great attention to their welfare, especially psychological well-being. It is because psychological well-being can affect all aspects of human resource performance. The theoretical framework in this study explores various stressors and their correlation to the commitment and performance of police personnel. These stressors are intrinsic factors to job,

organizational context, employee roles in an organization, career development, relationships at work, and sources of extra organizational stress such as family, physical or mental illness. The results of this study are surprisingly different from previous studies on the relationship between stressors and commitment and performance.

In general, stressors tested in this study did not harm the commitment of police officers working in complex and conflict-prone economic sectors such as the mining sector. The only negative stressor is the organizational context, which is quite reasonable considering the challenging and dangerous work climate that demands high flexibility from the police. However, it is worth noting that although some stressors do not have a significant effect, the negative influence of stressors such as factors Intrinsic to the job and extra organizational factors is known to exist and can have a negative impact on commitment.

The existence of these two stressors and their negative effect on performance indicate that job factors such as resource support and the nature of the job, such as the risk of danger, bad physical environment, dangerous workplace conditions, uncomfortable working hours, and excessive workload, are indeed experienced by police officers who work in mining areas. In addition, external influences such as family and socio-political issues also become an integral part that can potentially disrupt the commitment and performance of police personnel. Although it does not have a significant effect, the organization should pay attention to these two constructs through the support of adequate resources, creating a conducive work climate and a balance between personal and organizational life.

The results indicated that the police officers have a high organizational commitment, which can improve their performance. Some stressors proposed in this study are proved to be less significant to harm their organizational commitment. It should be noted that the police organization has its characteristics compared to other organizations. This peculiarity can be seen from the organization's ability to build a strong commitment within individual personnel since the personnel first attended education as a police officer. Strong ties and high solidity within the police organization are also factors that support the emergence of solid commitment even though this organization is identified as an organization that is prone to stress.

The differences in the research results described above open up opportunities for similar research to re-examine these various stressors and their relationship to commitment, performance, or other variables such as job satisfaction. In addition, the limited number of samples and coverage of the research locations can also be a consideration for conducting similar research in the future with a larger sample and more excellent coverage of the location.

References

1. Andrews, T., Elizalde, B., Le Billon, P., Oh, C. H., Reyes, D., & Thomson, I. (2017). The rise in conflict associated with mining operations: What lies beneath. Canadian International Resources and Development Institute (CIRDI), 1-127.
2. ASTUTY, I., & Udin, U. D. I. N. (2020). The effect of perceived organizational support and

- transformational leadership on affective commitment and employee performance. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 7(10), 401-411.
3. Baek, H. (2020). Perceived appropriateness of training and organizational commitment among Korean police. *International Criminal Justice Review*, 30, 235–253. *BMJ Open* 3, 1–12. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2013-002791
 4. Brown, J. (2000). Occupational culture as a factor in the stress experiences of police officers
 5. Brown, J. M., & Campbell, E. A. (1990). Sources of occupational stress in the police. *Work and Stress*, 4(4), 305–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678379008256993>
 6. Brunetto, Y., Teo, S. T. T., Farr-Wharton, R., Shacklock, K., & Shriberg, A. (2017). Individual and organizational support: Does it affect red tape, stress and work outcomes of police officers in the USA? *Personnel Review*, 46(4), 750–766. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-12-2015-0319>
 7. Burke, R. J., and Deszca, E. (1986). Correlates of psychological burnout phases among police officers. *Hum. Relat.* 39, 487–501. doi: 10.1177/001872678603900601
 8. Cartwright, S., & Cooper, C. L. (2014). Towards organizational health: Stress, positive organizational behavior, and employee well-being. *Bridging occupational, organizational and public health*, 29-42.
 9. Chan, J. (2007). Police stress and occupational culture. *Sociology of Crime, Law and Deviance*, 8, 129-151.
 10. Cicei, C. C. (2012). Occupational stress and organizational commitment in Romanian public organizations. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 33, 1077-1081.
 11. Cooke, R. A., & Rousseau, D. M. (1984). Stress and strain from family roles and work-role expectations. *Journal of applied psychology*, 69(2), 252.
 12. Cropanzano, R., Rupp, D. E., & Byrne, Z. S. (2003). The relationship of emotional exhaustion to work attitudes, job performance, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 88(1), 160.
 13. Dewe, P. J., O’Driscoll, M. P., & Cooper, C. L. (2012). Theories of psychological stress at work. In R. J. Gatchel & I. Z. Schultz (Eds.), *Handbook of occupational health and wellness* (pp. 23– 38). New York: Springer.
 14. Donald, I., Taylor, P., Johnson, S., Cooper, C., Cartwright, S., & Robertson, S. (2005). Work environments, stress, and productivity: An examination using ASSET. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 12(4), 409.
 15. Duran, F., Woodhams, J., & Bishopp, D. (2019). An interview study of the experiences of police officers in regard to psychological contract and wellbeing. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 34(2), 184-198.
 16. Duran, F., Woodhams, J., & Bishopp, D. (2019). An interview study of the experiences of police officers in regard to psychological contract and wellbeing. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 34(2), 184-198.
 17. Frank, J., Lambert, E. G., Qureshi, H., Myer, A. J., Klahm, C. F., Smith, B., & Hogan, N. L. (2020). Disentangling the direct and indirect effects of task, individual, and organizational factors on occupational citizenship behavior. *Criminal Justice*
 18. Ganster, C.C., Fusilier, M.R., & Mayes, B.T. (1986). Role of social support in the experience of stress at work. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71, 102–110
 19. Gold AH, Arvind Malhotra AH 2001 *J. Manage. Inform. Syst.* 18 185-214.
 20. Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139–152. <https://doi.org/10.2753/MTP1069-6679190202>
 21. Hakanen, J. J., Schaufeli, W. B., & Ahola, K. (2008). The Job Demands-Resources model: A three-year cross-lagged study of burnout, depression, commitment, and work engagement. *Work & stress*, 22(3), 224-241.
 22. Hammad, M., Awan, S. H., Akhtar, C., & Imdadullah, M. (2012). Investigating stress and employee performance in traffic police. *Work*, 21(1), 141-144.
 23. Hart, P. M., Wearing, A. J., & Headey, B. (1993). Assessing police work experiences: Development of the police daily hassles and uplifts scales. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 21(6), 553-572.
 24. He, N., Zhao, J., & Archbold, A. (2002). Gender and police stress: The convergent and divergent impact of work environment, work-family conflict, and stress coping mechanisms of female and male police officers. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies and Management*, 25(4), 687–708

25. Hunter, L. W., & Thatcher, S. M. (2007). Feeling the heat: Effects of stress, commitment, and job experience on job performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(4), 953-968.
26. Jagannathan, A. (2014). Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance. *International journal of productivity and performance management*. Vol. 63 No. 3, pp. 308-323.
27. James, L. R., James, L. A., and Ashe, D. K. (1990). The meaning of organizations: The role of cognition and values. In: B. Schneider (Ed.), *Organizational climate and culture* (pp. 40- 84). San Francisco, CA: Jossey Bass.
28. Jaramillo, F., Nixon, R., & Sams, D. (2005). The effect of law enforcement stress on organizational commitment. *Policing*, 28(2), 321–336. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13639510510597933>
- Jex, S. M., Beehr, T. A., & Roberts, C. K. (1992). The meaning of occupational stress items to survey respondents. *Journal of applied psychology*, 77(5), 623.
29. Johnson, R. R. (2015). Police organizational commitment: The influence of supervisor feedback and support. *Crime & Delinquency*, 61, 1155–1180.
30. Jonyo, E. O. (2015). Effects of Occupational Stress on Work Performance of Police Officers in Nakuru Police Division, Kenya. *IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR-JCE)* e-ISSN: 2278-0661, p-ISSN: 2278, 8727, 61-88.
31. Kadir, A., & Suaib, E. (2020). Mining in Southeast Sulawesi and Central Sulawesi: Shadow Economy and Environmental Damage Regional Autonomy Era in Indonesia. In *International Conference on Social Studies and Environmental Issues (ICOSSEI 2019)* (pp. 20-27). Atlantis Press.
32. Kawiana, I. G. P., Dewi, L. K. C., Hartati, P. S., Setini, M., & Asih, D. (2021). Effects of Leadership and Psychological Climate on Organizational Commitment in the Digitization Era. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(1), 1051–1062. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no1.1051>
33. Kiely, J. A., & Peek, G. S. (2002). The culture of the British police: Views of police officers. *Service industries journal*, 22(1), 167-183.
34. Kline RB 2011 *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling Third Edition* (NewYork: The Guilford Press)
35. Kristof-Brown, A. L., Zimmerman, R. D., & Johnson, E. C. (2005). Consequences of individual's fit at work: A meta-analysis of person-job, person-organization, person-group, and person-supervisor fit. *Personnel Psychology*, 58(2), 281– 342. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2005.00672.x>
36. Kuo, S. Y. (2015). Occupational stress, job satisfaction, and affective commitment to policing among Taiwanese police officers. *Police Quarterly*, 18(1), 27-54.
37. Lambert, E. G., Qureshi, H., & Frank, J. (2021). The good life: Exploring the effects job stress, job involvement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment on the life satisfaction of police officers. *International Journal of Police Science & Management*, 146135572111016494.
38. Lucas, T., Weidner, N., and Janisse, J. (2012). Where does work stress come from? A generalizability analysis of stress in police officers. *Psychol. Health* 27, 1426–1447. doi: 10.1080/08870446.2012.687738
39. Magnavita, N., Capitanelli, I., Garbarino, S., and Pira, E. (2018). Work-related stress as a cardiovascular risk factor in police officers: a systematic review of evidence. *Int. Arch. Occup. Environ. Health* 91, 377–389. doi: 10.1007/s00420- 018- 1290- y
40. Mansell, A., and Brough, P. (2005). A comprehensive test of the job demandscontrol interaction: Comparing two measures of job characteristics. *Australian Journal of*
41. Mansoor, M., Fida, S., Nasir, S., & Ahmad, Z. (2011). The impact of job stress on employee job satisfaction a study on telecommunication sector of Pakistan. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 2(3), 50.
42. Marois, A., Cloutier, M. S., Saunier, N., Godillon, S., Lafond, D., & Vachon, F. (2019). Safety, stress and work zone complexity: a field study on police officers performing on-foot traffic control. *Transportation research interdisciplinary perspectives*, 1, 100018.
43. Mathieu, J. E., & Zajac, D. M. (1990). A review and meta-analysis of the antecedents, correlates, and consequences of organizational commitment. *Psychological bulletin*, 108(2), 171.
44. McCarty, W. P., & Skogan, W. G. (2013). Job-related burnout among civilian and sworn police personnel. *Police quarterly*, 16(1), 66-84.
45. McCarty, W. P., Zhao, J., & Garland, B. E. (2007). *Policing : An International Journal of Police Strategies*

- & Management Article information : Occupational Stress and Burnout between Male and Female Police Officers: Are There Any Gender Differences?, 30(4), 672–691.
46. Mensah, J.K. (2015), “A ‘coalesced framework’ of talent management and employee performance: for further research and practice”, *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol. 64 No. 4, pp. 544-566.
 47. Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace: Theory, research, and application*. Sage publications. Page 30 of 37 <https://mc.manuscriptcentral.com/upm-ijem> *International Journal of Economics and Management*
 48. Meyer, J., & Allen, N. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace, theory research and application*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
 49. Motowidlo, S. J., Packard, J. S., & Manning, M. R. (1986). Occupational stress: its causes and consequences for job performance. *Journal of applied psychology*, 71(4), 618.
 50. Nalla, M. K., Akhtar, S., & Lambert, E. G. (2020). Exploring the connection between job satisfaction and different forms of organizational commitment among police. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 47, 511–528.
 51. Narayanan, L., Menon, S., & Spector, P. E. (1999). Stress in the workplace: A comparison of gender and occupations. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 20(1), 63-73.
 52. Nguyen, H. M., & Ngo, T. T. (2020). Psychological capital, organizational commitment and job performance: A case in Vietnam. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(5), 269–278. <https://doi.org/10.13106/JAFEB.2020.VOL7.NO5.269>
 53. Nisar, S. K., & Rasheed, M. I. (2020). Stress and performance: Investigating relationship between occupational stress, career satisfaction, and job performance of police employees. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 20(1), e1986.
 54. Nugraha, B. P. (2017). *Konflik Pertambangan Emas Antara Pemerintah Daerah, Perusahaan dan Masyarakat Gunung Tumpang Pitu di Kabupaten Banyuwangi* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Airlangga).
 55. Parker, C. P., Baltes, B. B., Young, S. A., Hu, J. W., Altmann, R. A., Lacost, H. A., & Roberts, J. E. (2003). Relationships between psychological climate perceptions and work outcomes: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 24 (4), 389-416. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.198>
 56. Parker, D. F., & DeCotiis, T. A. (1983). Organizational determinants of job stress. *Organizational behavior and human performance*, 32(2), 160-177.
 57. Qureshi, H., Lambert, E. G., & Frank, J. (2019). When domains spill over: The relationships of work-family conflict with Indian police affective and continuance commitment. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 63, 2501–2525.
 58. Resosudarmo, B. P., Resosudarmo, I. A. P., Sarosa, W., & Subiman, N. L. (2009). *Socioeconomic conflicts in Indonesia's mining industry. Exploiting Natural Resources: Growth, Instability, and Conflict in the Middle East and Asia*, Washington, DC: The Henry L. Stimson Center, 33-48.
 59. Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2013). *Organizational behavior* (Vol. 4). New Jersey: Pearson Education.
 60. Rothmann, S., & Pienaar, J. (2006). Occupational stress in the South African police service. *SA journal of Industrial Psychology*, 32(3), 72-78.
 61. Rothmann, S., & Pienaar, J. (2006). Occupational stress in the South African police service. *SA journal of Industrial Psychology*, 32(3),
 62. Thompson, B. M., Kirk, A., & Brown, D. F. (2005). Work based support, emotional exhaustion, and spillover of work stress to the family environment: A study of policewomen. *Stress and Health*, 21(3), 199-207.
 63. Van Thanh, L. (2016). Relationship at work as a cause of occupational stress: the case of academic women in Vietnam. *International journal of mental health systems*, 10, 1-15.